

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SHAMPOO

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ABSTRACT

A shampoo is a preparation containing a suitable surfactant (i.e. surface-active material) liquid, solid or powder-which, when used under the prescribed conditions, removes surface grease, dirt and skin debris from the hair shaft and scalp without adversely affecting the user. Various anti-fungal agents are used for the dandruff procedure in hair care preparations. Such drugs show various side effects such as hair loss, increased scaling, scratching, discomfort, nausea and headache. Therefore, an attempt was made to Formation and evaluation of herbal neem-based shampoo that is safer in terms of health and treating the dandruff condition than the anti-dandruff shampoo based on chemicals. Herbal anti-dandruff shampoos have been formulated using herbal ingredients such as other ingredients for base shampoo preparations. The formulated shampoos were Amla, Reetha, Shikakai, Onion seeds, Lemon, Aloe vera, Guava leaves, Custard apple leaves, rose water, subjected to evaluation parameters such as visual inspection, pH, viscosity, solid content percentage, dirt dispersion, surface tension, foaming capacity and consistency of the foam, Pityrosporum Ovale strain anti-fungal activity test. Formulation (F4) showed strong antifungal activity, i.e., maximum inhibitory region.

Key words: Herbal Shampoo, Amla, Aloe Vera gel, Anti-dandruff, pH

Introduction

There are many different types of shampoos available today, which include synthetic, herbal, medicated, and non-medicated varieties, but consumers are becoming more and more interested in herbal shampoo because they think that because these products come from natural sources, they are risk-free and without side effects (Mainkar and Jolly, 2001).

Although creating cosmetics with just natural ingredients is challenging, herbal formulations are thought to be an alternative to synthetic shampoo. Numerous medicinal herbs are frequently included in shampoo formulations and are said to have positive benefits on hair. These plant-based materials can be utilised as derivatives, powder, crude, or pure extracts (Arora et al., 2011).

Like ordinary shampoo, herbal shampoos are made with natural components and are designed to

clean the hair and scalp. Because they don't include surfactants, these shampoos are less hazardous than synthetic shampoos and have superior stability. Long-term usage of the surfactants included in synthetic shampoo can have detrimental consequences such as skin irritation, split ends, dry hair, greying hair, and irritation of the scalp. Because of these factors, the public is becoming more interested in herbal cosmetics because of its low cost and negligible adverse effects.

History

The Indian subcontinent has long produced shampoos utilising a variety of botanicals and their extracts. Shampoo originated in the Indus Valley Civilisation. A very powerful early shampoo was made by boiling Sapindus with dried Indian gooseberry (amla) and a number of other herbs using the filtered extract. The tropical tree Sapindus, sometimes called soapberries or soapnuts, is referred to as ksuna in ancient Indian texts.

Shampoo

Most likely, shampoos are utilised as cosmetics. It is a hair care product that we use on a regular basis to clean our hair and scalp. Shampoos are probably used as beautifying agents and a thick mixture of detergents with active chemicals, preservatives, and appropriate additions. Typically, it is applied to damp hair, massaged into the hair, and then rinsed with water to clean. Shampoo is used to get rid of accumulated filth from the hair.

Types of Shampoo

- Powder shampoo
- Liquid shampoo
- Lotion shampoo
- Cream shampoo
- Jelly shampoo
- Aerosol shampoo

Benefits of herbal shampoo

- More shine
- Less hair loss
- Remove dandruff
- Long lasting colour
- Promote hair growth.

- All natural, no chemicals
- Keep healthy natural oils
- Keep healthy natural oils
- Won't irritate skin or scalp
- Stronger and more fortified hairs

Hair Antamony (Figure 1)

95% of the hair is composed of keratin, a fibrous, helicoidal protein that makes up the epidermis and all of its attachments, including the nails and body hair. There are three distinct components to the hair structure:

Medulla: The deepest layer of the hair shaft is called the medulla, and it is composed of soft, greasy, amorphous substances.

Cuticle: A thin, protective outer layer that is rich in nutrients that promote hair development. It is highly keratinised, with cells around 60 micrometres long and 6 micrometres broad that resemble scales and are piled one on top of the other.

Cortex: The cortex, the primary component of hair, is made up of long keratin chains that give the hair its elasticity, suppleness, and resilience.

Figure 1: Shows Hair Anatomy

Hair Problem

Hair loss, infections, and conditions that cause itching and scaling are common issues that affect the hair and scalp. Despite the fact that it is normal to lose some hair every day, hair loss (alopecia) is a common problem for both men and women.

Hair Loss

Hair loss, also known as alopecia, can have a variety of causes. In men, the most common cause of hair loss is male pattern baldness, which is a hereditary condition that results in hair loss on the top of the head and the temples in women, the most common cause of hair loss is female pattern baldness, which also results in hair loss on the top of the head, but usually does not result in complete baldness (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Shows Hair Loss

Dandruff

Dandruff is a common condition that affects the scalp and causes flaking of the skin. Dandruff is usually caused by a combination of factors, including dry skin, oily skin, and the presence of a yeast-like fungus called *Malassezia*. In this article, we will discuss the causes and treatments of dandruff (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Shows Hair dandruff

Fungal Infection

Fungal infections of the scalp can lead to a variety of symptoms, including itching, redness, scaling, and hair loss. These infections are usually caused by dermatophytes, a group of fungi that thrive on keratin, a protein found in hair, skin, and nails. In this article, we will discuss the causes, symptoms, and treatments of fungal infections of the hair (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Shows Fungal infection

Material and Methods

Herbal Shampoo Material

The Herbs and powders used in present formulation work have been procured from authenticated supplier and are research grade some material obtained from pharmacognosy lab and some are obtained from marketed as mentioned below in Table 1.

Table 1: Shows List of materials collected

Sr.no	Materials	Source
1	Amla	From market
2	Reetha	From market
3	Shikakai	Cognosy lab
4	Onion seeds	From Farm
5	Lemon	From market
6	Aloe vera	From market

7	Guava leaves	From farm
8	Custard apple leaves	From farm

Ingridients

Amla

Amla has a tone of essential fatty acids that get into the hair follicles and give the hair more volume, shine, and softness. Due to its high iron and carotene content, it also o promotes the growth of new hair. Amla can be mixed with other herbs that encourage hair development to make an Amla paste for hair (Khan et al., 2022).

Reetha

A common aspect of Herbal shampoos and cleansers is Sapindus mukorossi. They are applied in Ayurvedic medicine to treat psoriasis, eczema, and freckles. Reetha is antibacterial and antifungal in nature. With regular use, any scalp infection including dandruff is treated (Bouillon, 1996).

Shikakai

The dried pods of Acacia concinna (Shikakai), a member of the Mimosaceae family, are well recognized for their use as a foam base, anti-dandruff treatment, cleaning agent, and to remove filth and oil from the scalp. Shikakai shampoo and oil have antifungal characteristics that hydrate the scalp and lessen flakiness, dryness, and itching (Yadav and Mohite, 2020).

Onion Seed

The onion (*Allium cepa*), which is a belonging to the genus *Allium* and family Amaryllidaceae, is a well-known spice that most originally comes in the south-west of Asia Researchers have discovered that onions' anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties may boost hair growth or increase the appearance of healthy hair (Mendhekar et al., 2017).

Lemon

Lemons are grown on spiny, small trees that are 10 to 20 feet tall. The lemons alternately positioned, dark green leaves are grouped on the stalk. Shampoo's pH can be lowered by the use of citric acid to make it healthier for your scalp and hair. It also boosts your hair follicles because to its antioxidant characteristics, which minimize hair breakage and thinning.

Aloe vera

Aloe vera plants have been used by humans for a variety of reasons since 1750 BC. There are around 450 species of aloe vera. This succulent plant grows in arid, hot climates. For thousands of

years, people have utilised aloe vera for its therapeutic qualities. It is good for general health since it is full of vitamins, minerals, and nutrients (D'Souza and Rathi, 2015).

Guava Leaves

Guava leaves have an entire margin, an exstipulate shape, a short petiole, an oval or acuminate apex, and a rounded to sub acuminate base. They are greenish in color. Guava leaves contain antibacterial and antifungal qualities that can help to prevent infections on your scalp. Guava leaves are known for their numerous health benefits, and they are also great for hair (Vinayak et al., 2019).

Custard Leaves

A common tree in India's several agro-dimatic zones is the tiny, semi-deciduous *Annona squamosa* Linn. (Annonaceae) tree, which grows 3 to 7 meters tall and has a broad, open crown or irregularly spreading branches. Due to the presence of antioxidant vitamins A and C in custard apple leaves, they are also good for the skin. Custard apple leaves have natural antifungal properties that can help control scalp infections such as dandruff and other fungal infections (Maurya et al., 2021).

Process of Material Preparation

1. Weight the whole ingredient and extract given in table by weighing balance.
2. Weighted 10 gm powder of Amla, Shikakai, Reetha, Onion seed, Guava leaves and Custard apple leaves. Boiled separately in 50 ml on water bath for 30 min. to get liquid extract of this powder.
3. After boiling filter it separately.
4. Mix the Amla, Shikakai, Reetha, Onion seed, Guava leaves and Custard apple leaves extract in mortar and pestle.
5. Add Methyl paraben, Sodium lauryl sulphate in it triturate properly.
6. Add aloe vera, Rose water, Glycerin in the above mixture.
7. Measure the quantity and make up the volume 100 ml by adding water as per q.s.
8. Evaluate the prepare shampoo and take reading.

Evaluations Parameter

Preparation and Evaluation of Herbal Shampoo

To evaluate the quality of commercial and prepared formulations, several quality control tests including visual assessment, physicochemical controls conditioning performance tests were performed.

Physically Appearance

The formulations prepared were evaluated in terms of their clarity, thick, semi white transparent in color, great foam producing ability and fluidity (Kumar and Mali, 2010).

Determination of pH:

Mix 1ml of shampoo with 100ml of water and determine the pH using Standardizes digital pH meter at 27°C (Aghel et al., 2010).

Foam ability and Stability

The ability to produce foam was evaluated using the cylinder shake method. A 250 ml graduated cylinder was filled with 50 ml of the 1% HS solution, then the cylinder was covered with a hand and gently shook ten times. After shaking for a minute, the total quantities of the foam contents were measured. Only the foam volume was computed. The amount of foam was measured immediately after shaking and at 1-minute intervals for 4 minutes. 120 ml of foam are produced of HS (Balsam et al., 2008).

Solubility

2 ml of shampoo is added to 100 ml of water. The solution formed was well shaken and then heated to increase solubility. After 10 mins of heating the solution was cooled down and then the quantity of residue was noted (Badi and Khan, 2014).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Shows test results of herbal shampoo

Sr.no	Parameters	Observations
1	Color	Brown
2	Odor	Good
3	Transparency	Not transparent
4	Determination of pH	5.9(Acidic)
5	Foam volume(ml)	120 ml
6	Solubility	Insoluble in water
7	Skin irritation test	No irritation
8	Wetting time test	5 sec
9	Determination of density	25.7 gm

The shampoo's formulation was transparent and attractive. It performed well in terms of stability, detergency, cleaning, tiny bubble size, minimal surface strain, and conditioning. Herbal shampoos

are formulations that are used to wash, clean, and nourish hair. Because they include only natural or herbal components instead of artificial chemicals, herbal shampoos are more popular than conventional shampoos because they have fewer or no adverse effects. Herbal shampoo is safe for skin and doesn't need to be tested on animals. Several ingredients were combined in precise ratios to create the herbal shampoo. They have been shown to have anti-dandruff, anti-hairfall, cleaning, moisturising, and surfactant qualities. The herbal shampoo's physicochemical characteristics were assessed statistically. The efficacy of a herbal shampoo that contains Amla, Reetha, Shikakai, onion seeds, lemon, aloe vera, guava leaves, custard apple leaves, rose water, sodium lauryl sulphate, glycerin, and methyl paraben might vary based on a number of factors, including the type and condition of each person's hair. There is little scientific study focused on the combination of these substances in shampoo form, despite the fact that they are frequently utilised in ayurveda and herbal hair care therapies.

CONCLUSION

In addition to having antibacterial and antifungal properties, the shampoo's formulation significantly slows down hair loss and promotes hair growth. The shampoo's pH was changed to 6.2 in order to preserve the scalp's acidic mantle. The formulations were preserved using a physicochemical method to reduce the danger associated with chemical preservatives. The commercial shampoos and the laboratory shampoo are not similar in terms of clarity. Even if herbal shampoos are safer and more effective than synthetic ones, it doesn't seem likely that people will use them in the current situation. It is imperative that consumers' ideas of a good shampoo be changed, and the formulators are responsible for this.

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